

Supporting Information:

Combining freestanding ferroelectric perovskite oxides with two-dimensional semiconductors for high performance transistors

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Figure S1. Thickness determination of thin BTO flakes using optical contrast. (a) Optical microscopy images of BTO flakes on 285 nm of SiO₂ on Si substrates. The change in color corresponds to a change in the flake thickness. (b) AFM scans of the same flakes as in panel (a).

Figure S2. Raman and photoluminescence spectroscopy of MoS₂ on BTO. (a) Optical image of one of the devices with MoS₂ on BTO. The green dot shows the location of the laser for the measurement of MoS₂ on SiO₂. (b) Raman spectrum of MoS₂ on SiO₂/Si substrate. (c) Photoluminescence spectra of MoS₂ on BTO and MoS₂ on SiO₂/Si. The photoluminescence spectra on top of BTO shows a more prominent contribution from the neutral A excitons than the spectra onto SiO₂.

Figure S3. Local PFM amplitude and phase hysteresis curves acquired on additional transferred BTO flakes. (a-c) AFM topography scans of the flakes. (d-f) Local PFM amplitude for the same flakes shown in panels (a-c). (g-i) Local PFM phase for the corresponding flakes in (a-c). The darker black curves in (d) to (i) are the average over the individual hysteresis curves acquired on the flakes.

Table S1. Summary of device characteristics for all devices measured. Values are reported for both the forward and back sweeps considering the hysteresis present in the gate sweeps. The width and length columns pertain to the semiconducting channel dimensions and the thickness column refers to the thickness of the BTO or hBN dielectric flake. (SS = subthreshold swing).

Name	ON/OFF Ratio	Hysteresis (V)	Forward Mobility (cm ² /V*s)	Back Mobility (cm ² /V*s)	Forward SS (V/dec)	Back SS (V/dec)	Width (μm)	Length (μm)	Thickness (nm)
BTO_1	2 · 10 ⁶	24.0	4.7	7.9	2.3	0.7	7	25.0	47.0
BTO_2	2 · 10 ⁵	29.5	6.1	8.6	5.2	4.8	7.0	25.0	48.0

BTO_7	$5 \cdot 10^5$	16.0	22.2	31.1	1.6	1.9	7.0	25.0	45.0
BTO_9	$3 \cdot 10^7$	35.0	35.1	18.0	0.5	0.7	29.0	25.0	48.0
BTO_10	$6 \cdot 10^0$	44.0	56.7	52.4	26.6	351.1	10.0	30.0	50.0
SiO₂_1	10^6	4.5	9.9	10.3	0.4	0.6	17.0	30.0	
hBN_3	$4 \cdot 10^{10}$	10.0	4.1	6.3	1.9	2.1	8.0	27.0	40.0
hBN_8	10^9	13.5	52.3	81.1	1.4	1.2	22	25.0	42.0
hBN_10	$2 \cdot 10^5$	33.0	1.5	0.9	1.4	1.9	15	25.0	34.0
hBN_11	$2 \cdot 10^8$	7.0	30.7	29.9	1.0	1.3	12	30.0	28.0